

ELIXIR Commissioned Service
2024-TECHNOLOGY-TRAINING PLATFORM
Work Package 1 - Governance of the Training Platform

M1.2 Annual Platform meeting

Tier: Technology

Executive Summary

This TrP milestone report links to the published Annual Platform Meeting report.

Author List

Node	Institution	Name	ORCID
ES-Spain	Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)	Eva Alloza	0000-0001-8385-9336
GR-Greece	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas (EKETA/CERTH)	Fotis Psomopoulos	0000-0002-0222-4273
SE-Sweden	Umeå University	Jessica Lindvall	0000-0002-5042-8481
Hub		Katharina Heil	0000-0003-3341-3736
Hub		Mihail Anton	0000-0002-7753-9042

Report

The 2025 ELIXIR Training Platform hybrid meeting was hosted in Munich, Germany from March 27–28 2025. A full report has been published on Zenodo and can be found [here](#).

Dissemination Plans

Publishing the report on Zenodo makes it citable as a digital object.